

PGD-MAT

IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE

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INTRODUCTION

What is PGD-MAT?

The Brazilian *Programa de Gestão e Desempenho (PGD)* signifies a modernization of federal public administration, shifting from a model focused on physical presence to one centered on deliverables, results, and trust. However, effective implementation of the PGD encounters challenges, particularly in organizations that are still in the process of developing their performance management and monitoring practices.

In this context, PGD-MAT, a Maturity Model, that serves as a diagnostic tool, enabling teams, units, and agencies to identify their current stage of maturity in implementing the essential practices of the PGD. It provides clear guidance for the evolution and continuous improvement of the PGD within public organizations.

The development of PGD-MAT was informed by established theoretical frameworks and management models from both literature and industry, including CMMI, MPS-RH, Agile Methodologies, and OKR. These were adapted to fit the normative and practical realities of the PGD in Brazilian federal public administration.

Why use this guide?

This Practical Guide has been created to help managers, human resources teams, and employees effectively utilize the PGD-MAT. It provides a clear, step-by-step approach, guiding users from self-assessment to the development and monitoring of an improvement plan tailored to the specific needs of your organization.

The Two Views of PGD-MAT

To provide a complete diagnosis, PGD-MAT uses two complementary assessment approaches:

PGD Maturity Level (Staged View)

It provides an overview of the organization, classifying it into one of five levels (**1 - Initial to 5 - Excellence**). This overview is useful for initial communication and for understanding the predominant characteristics of the execution of the PGD in the organization.

Dimension Capability Levels (Continuous View)

The overview includes a detailed profile of the organization's performance across five dimensions of the model:

- 1. Planning:** The organization's ability to develop structured delivery and work plans with clear goals that align with its institutional strategy.
- 2. Execution of Tasks:** The organization and management of daily activities, which involve employee autonomy and team adaptability.
- 3. Performance Evaluation:** Processes for monitoring, analyzing, and providing feedback on both individual and collective performance.
- 4. Training, Engagement, and Culture:** The level of knowledge, commitment, well-being, sense of purpose, and social connections within the work environment.
- 5. Tools and Data:** The use of technologies, records, and data to support performance management and decision-making.

The results are expressed as numerical values (e.g., Planning 3.8, Evaluation 2.1), indicating not only the current consolidated level but also the progress toward the next level. This overview is crucial for guiding improvement efforts in a precise and prioritized manner.

At the end of this guide, you will find Appendix A, which details the expected characteristics of the organization for each dimension at each maturity level.

The Four Steps of Implementation

The application of PGD-MAT and the implementation of improvements are organized into four main steps:

STEP 1: Preparation

Assemble the team and define the project scope.

STEP 2: Diagnosis

Administer the questionnaire and interpret the results.

STEP 3: Action Planning

Develop an action plan.

STEP 4: Execution and Continuous Improvement

Execute the plan and measure progress.

STEP 1: PREPARATION

Preparation of the team that will conduct the subsequent steps of the model implementation and definition of the scope of the evaluation.

Step 1.1: Define the Working Group (WG)

Who should participate?

It is recommended to have a multidisciplinary group.

- **Working Group Leader:** A manager with a broad understanding of the organization.
- **Management Representatives:** Team leaders and managers.
- **Representatives of the employees:** Employees from various departments and backgrounds who are involved in the PGD.

Role of the Working Group (WG)

The WG is responsible for managing the process, ensuring engagement, consolidating results, and leading the development of the action plan.

Step 1.2: Define the Scope of the Assessment

Which unit will be evaluated?

The maturity model can be applied to a specific team, a sector, a directorate, or the organization as a whole. It is crucial to clearly define the scope to ensure alignment among all those involved.

What assessment format will be used?

It has yet to be determined whether the evaluation will focus on **maturity levels** or **capabilities**, concentrating on one or more dimensions.

Initial Communication

The working group must communicate the purpose of the evaluation to the entire unit, emphasizing that the objective is to promote **improvement** and not to assign blame or seek out who is at fault.

STEP 2: DIAGNOSIS

It is time to implement the PGD-MAT and evaluate the current maturity level of the organization.

Step 2.1: Conduct the Self-Assessment

Using the maturity assessment spreadsheet, the Working Group gathers to evaluate each attribute of the PGD-MAT based on the chosen assessment type. They aim to reach a **consensus** on the scores, which can be categorized as No (0), Sometimes (0.5), or Yes (1). This consensus meeting approach encourages meaningful discussions, aligns perceptions, and enhances engagement with the results.

In the context of the PGD-MAT, attributes refer to the practices that an organization is expected to perform within a specific dimension and at a particular maturity level. For example, under the dimension of Planning, at Level 2 - Managed, the expected attribute is “[PLA2.1] The unit has a delivery plan for the current year.” This indicates that the organizational unit is expected to have a plan outlining the desired deliverables for the current year.

Attention: For each attribute, one must seek **evidence**

"Where do we see this happening?"

"Who can confirm this?"

"Is this an isolated practice or is it the standard?"

Step 2.2: Consolidate and Analyze Results from the Self-Assessment

The GT leader consolidates the consensus responses by **assigning values to the attributes in the PGD-MAT spreadsheet assessment**, following the selected evaluation format (either by maturity levels or by capacity). The formulas implemented in this spreadsheet will automatically calculate the results for maturity or capacity based on the assigned values: No - 0, Sometimes - 0.5, or Yes - 1.

Analysis of the Results: The working group convenes again to analyze the results for the maturity or capabilities obtained from the evaluation spreadsheet.

- Maturity Level Analysis (Overview):** In this analysis, we evaluate the results by identifying the dimensions that contributed to them. If a dimension has an average score of 0.75 or higher, it is considered to be **met**. Conversely, if the average score for a dimension is below 0.75, it is deemed **not met**. A maturity level is **achieved** when **all dimensions meet the required standards**. For example, Figure 1 illustrates an assessment that reached maturity level 3.

Figure 1. Assessment that reached maturity level 3.

Relevant reflections:

"What is the overall maturity level of the unit?"

"What does the result obtained mean in practical terms, based on the description of the levels?"

"In which dimensions did we achieve a good result?"

- **Analysis of Capability Levels:** This analysis aims to identify the capability level (ranging from 1 - Initial to 5 - Excellence) for the evaluated dimensions. In this context, the classification rules for "He meets" and "Does not meet" also apply. However, the final result will be a numerical value.

			PLANNING	
LEVEL	AVERAGE	SITUATION	ATTRIBUTE	ASSESSMENT
2	0,77	MET	[PLA2.1] The unit has a delivery plan for the current year.	Sometimes -
			[PLA2.2] For each deliverable in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined target.	Yes -
			[PLA2.3] For each delivery in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined deadline.	Sometimes -
			[PLA2.4] For each deliverable in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined requester.	Sometimes -
			[PLA2.5] For each delivery in the unit's delivery plan, there is a defined recipient.	Yes -
			[PLA2.6] The unit's delivery plan is reviewed at defined intervals.	Yes -
			[PLA2.7] Each member of the PGD has an individual work plan.	Sometimes -
			[PLA2.8] Individual work plans indicate their period of validity.	Sometimes -
			[PLA2.9] Individual work plans indicate the distribution of the owner's working hours during the period of validity.	Yes -
			[PLA2.10] The criteria that will be used by the supervisor to evaluate the individual work plan are defined in the individual work plans.	Yes -
			[PLA2.11] Individual work plans are derived from, or explicitly aligned with, the deliverables defined in the unit plan.	Yes -
3	0,67	NOT MET	[PLA3.1] The organization uses OKR, defining measurable operational goals.	Sometimes -
			[PLA3.2] Team members contribute to defining cycle goals.	Sometimes -
			[PLA3.3] The progress toward the defined goals is frequently reviewed and updated.	Yes -
			[PLA3.4] Operational goals are reviewed and redefined periodically.	No -
			[PLA3.5] Operational goals are broken down into team deliverables.	Yes -
			[PLA3.6] Team deliverables are broken down into individual plan deliverables for their members, allowing for traceability of the origin.	Yes -
4	0,43	NOT MET	[PLA4.1] Operational targets are estimated based on historical data.	Sometimes -
			[PLA4.2] Team deliverables are estimated based on historical data.	No -
			[PLA4.3] Individual deliveries are estimated based on historical data.	No -
			[PLA4.4] Risks and dependencies related to operational goals are identified and monitored.	Sometimes -
			[PLA4.5] The risks and dependencies related to team deliverables are identified and monitored.	Sometimes -
			[PLA4.6] Mitigation plans exist for targets with identified risks.	Yes -
			[PLA4.7] Mitigation plans exist for deliveries with identified risks.	Sometimes -
5	0,38	NOT MET	[PLA5.1] Planning occurs in an iterative manner, with adjustments made based on performance data.	No -
			[PLA5.2] There is a clear connection between operational goals and the actions outlined in the organization's tactical and strategic plans.	Sometimes -
			[PLA5.3] The definition of strategic goals is carried out with the participation of stakeholders.	No -
			[PLA5.4] As outlined in OKRs, some of the operational goals are defined by the team itself.	Yes -
Highest level completed				2
Next level progress				0,67
Capacity Level				2,67

Figure 2. Assessment of Capacity in the Planning Dimension.

Figure 2 presents the results of a capacity assessment for Dimension **Planning**. If the result obtained from this evaluation is **2.67**, we can interpret it as follows:

- The **integer part** (2) indicates that the highest capability level at which this dimension is classified as "He meets" is Level 2. This implies that the average of the attributes in this dimension is greater than or equal to (\geq) 0.75.
- The **fractional part** (0.67) indicates the progress toward the next level; in this case, Level 3, indicating that the organization is close to achieving the next capability level.

Relevant reflections:

- "Which dimension has the highest level of capability?"
- "Which dimensions have the lowest capacity levels?"
- "What are we doing well here that we can use as an example?"

Step 2.3: Identify Weak Points (Priorities):

Analyze the results and prioritize improvements based on the identified weaknesses.

"What dimensions need to be improved to reach the next level of maturity?"

"How to improve the capabilities of dimension Y."

STEP 3: ACTION PLANNING

Transform the diagnosis into a concrete action plan.

Step 3.1: Prioritize the Dimensions

Based on the analysis, the Working Group (WG) should prioritize a few dimensions (ideally 1 or 2), focusing mainly on those with the lowest capacity levels. The goal is to concentrate improvement efforts in the next cycle, which spans approximately three months.

Step 3.2: Create the Action Plan

For example, if the priority dimension is Performance Evaluation and its capacity level is 2.1, the WG should concentrate on the Level 2 attributes that have not yet been fully met (with a score of less than 1) as well as the Level 3 attributes (the next level).

Concrete Actions: The WG should examine the attributes of Levels 2 and 3 for this dimension and develop them into an actionable plan. This can be structured using a simple format such as "5W2H" (What, Why, Where, When, Who, How, How Much).

What?	Why?	Where?	When?	Who?	How?	How much?
Create a process for formally recording evaluations and feedback.	To create a history of performance to provide a basis for future decisions and ensure the formality of the process.	In the PGD management tool.	Definition of the process and tool in 2 months; implement in the next cycle.	Working Group (WG) of PGD-MAT, with support from the IT area (if necessary) and Human Resources.	Assess whether the available tools allow for registration.	There is no cost if you use existing tools. There may be a cost if the official tool needs to be modified.
Implement structured feedback sessions.	To improve communication, align performance, and connect individual work to the team's purpose.	In one-on-one meetings between managers and team members (in person or virtual).	Starting next month, frequency to be determined (e.g, monthly or bimonthly).	All team managers (direct leaders).	To carry out a <i>workshop</i> (online) for managers on effective feedback techniques and create a simple template (Google Docs/Word) to guide the conversation.	Zero cost (use of internal tools and managers' time). <i>Workshop</i> : It can be internal or, if external, the cost is to be determined.

Table 1. Example of an Action Plan
(Dimension: Performance Evaluation)

STEP 4: EXECUTION AND CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

Execute planned improvement actions.

Step 4.1: Execute and Monitor the Action Plan for Improvements

The Working Group (WG) is responsible for **monitoring the progress** of the improvement action plan. Holding regular follow-up meetings (e.g., monthly) is crucial to this process. It is important to **communicate** the progress of the initiatives to the entire unit, ensuring that everyone remains engaged.

Step 4.2: Reassess and Restart the Cycle of Assessment and Improvement

After a defined period (e.g., 3 to 4 months), the WG must **conduct a new self-assessment** using PGD-MAT. The goal is to measure progress, celebrate achievements, and define priorities for the next evaluation and improvement cycle.

CONCLUSION

The application of PGD-MAT, whether viewed through the lens of **Maturity Levels** or through a detailed analysis of **Capacity Levels**, should not be seen as an end in itself but rather as the beginning of a virtuous cycle. The true value of the Maturity Model lies in its ability to generate accurate assessments that foster constructive discussions and guide the development of action plans focused on the organization's real needs.

It's essential to emphasize that maturity in management and performance is not a final destination to be reached, but rather a continuous journey of learning, adaptation, and improvement. The practices outlined at the higher levels of the PGD-MAT represent a goal to strive for. However, each step taken and each improvement implemented based on the diagnosis signifies a significant advancement toward achieving more efficient, strategic, and humanized public management.

By adopting PGD-MAT, the organization is not just implementing a maturity model but also engaging in a process of reflection and organizational development aligned with the principles of continuous improvement.

APPENDIX A: DIMENSIONS x LEVELS

Planning dimension

- **Level 1:** Non-existent planning or planning carried out in a way *for this purpose*. Work is distributed as demand arises, without predictability or alignment with broader objectives.
- **Level 2:** It begins with basic formalization: having a unit "Delivery Plan" and individual "Work Plans." This is the minimum organizational stage.
- **Level 3:** The capability evolves towards the use of a structured method (OKR) and collaboration, with teams participating in defining goals and breaking them down to the individual level.
- **Level 4:** It achieves quantitative maturity by using historical data to estimate goals and deliverables and by introducing risk management.
- **Level 5:** It reaches the strategic and adaptive level, with iterative planning, full traceability to the organization's strategy, and empowering teams to define their own goals.

Task Execution Dimension

- **Level 1:** The execution is reactive and disorganized. Tasks are distributed and executed without a defined process, often based on emergency demands, and with little visibility into the team's work. The focus is on "putting out fires."
- **Level 2:** It focuses on assigning and monitoring basic tasks and on the existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for routine work.
- **Level 3:** It introduces workflow management through backlogs, defined cycles, and follow-up rituals (e.g., *daily meetings*).
- **Level 4:** Formalize the cycles with the concept of sprints, and, crucially, it introduces the cycle of feedback and improvement through review and retrospective meetings.
- **Level 5:** It achieves autonomy and optimization, with teams performing self-diagnostics, adjusting their own processes, and organizing themselves into cross-functional teams (*squads*).

Performance Evaluation Dimension

- **Level 1:** Non-existent or entirely informal. There is no structured evaluation process. Feedback, when it occurs, is sporadic, subjective, and reactive to isolated events, with no connection to goals or career development.
- **Level 2:** A monitoring ritual is established, with goal review, end-of-cycle evaluation, and periodic feedback.
- **Level 3:** The process becomes more formal and qualified, with clearer criteria, recording of results, and more structured feedback sessions.
- **Level 4:** It evolves into a quantitative assessment, with the use of *benchmarks* and SLAs.
- **Level 5:** It reaches its peak with 360° evaluation and a focus on collective learning.

Capacity Building, Engagement, and Culture Dimension

- **Level 1:** The environment is reactive and purely transactional. There are no planned actions for training, engagement, or cultural development. The culture is focused on the immediate task, with a low sense of collective purpose and little psychological safety.
- **Level 2:** Initial training and specific integration and recognition initiatives.
- **Level 3:** It evolves into structured processes: identifying skills gaps, periodic training, and formal listening spaces.
- **Level 4:** It becomes data-driven, with climate and engagement assessments generating institutional improvement plans.
- **Level 5:** It reaches a human-centered level, focusing on well-being, empowerment, a culture of recognition, and active monitoring of the mental health of employees.

Tools and Data Dimension

- **Level 1:** The use of basic and non-standardized tools. Management is based on individual controls. There is no centralized data source, which makes it impossible to generate performance indicators and make evidence-based decisions.
- **Level 2:** The capability is for recording and control. The tools serve to know the basics: what, who, when, and what the status is.
- **Level 3:** It evolves towards data and context generation. The tools begin to classify by complexity and consolidate historical data, generating the first indicators.
- **Level 4:** It achieves predictive capability. The tools begin to use historical data to support future decision-making.
- **Level 5:** The tools support strategic management, with full data integration, *Business Intelligence*, and *dashboards* in real time to support decisions at all levels.